

**EFFECT OF LOAN PORTFOLIO MANAGEMENT ON COMMERCIAL BANKS
LIQUIDITY**

Abstract

The study examined the effect of loan portfolio management on the liquidity position of commercial banks by specifically highlighting 2005 – 2014 financial year. This was targeted to identify the effect of asset quality ratio (AQR) on current asset of the commercial banks as well as to analyze the relationship between the loan to deposit ratio and the liquidity ratio of the banks. Secondary data was employed and a panel data was generated for a period specified for three 3 banks. Various theories such as the portfolio theory and credit risk theory suggested that banks should balance their loans which forms their major source of revenue with their liquidity. Banks by nature are inclined to lend as this activity ensures profitability. However, it is imperative to give cognizance to liquidity which ensures solvency of the banks because if the liquidity of banks is not sturdy it may create panic withdrawal.

CHAPTER ONE

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Lending is the principal business activity for most commercial banks. The loan portfolio is typically the largest asset and the predominate source of revenue. As such, it is one of the greatest sources of risk to a bank's liquidity.

The concept of loan can be traced back in history and it was not appreciated until and after the Second World War when it was largely appreciated in Europe and later in Africa (Kiiru, 2004). Banks in USA gave credit to customers with high interest rates which continue to discourage borrowers hence the concept of credit did not become popular until the economic boom in USA in 1885 when the banks had excess liquidity and wanted to lend the excess cash (Ditcher, 2003). Effective management of the loan portfolio and the credit function is fundamental to a bank's Liquidity. Loan portfolio management (LPM) is the process by which risks that are inherent in the credit process are managed and controlled. Because review of the LPM process is so important, it is a primary supervisory activity. Assessing LPM involves evaluating the steps bank management takes to identify and control risk throughout the credit process. The assessment focuses on what management does to identify issues before they become problems.

To manage their portfolios, bankers must understand not only the risk posed by each credit but also how the risks of individual loans and portfolios are interrelated. These interrelationships can multiply risk many times beyond what it would be if the risks were not related. Now, many banks view the loan portfolio in its segments and as a whole and consider the relationships among portfolio segments as well as among loans. These practices provide management with a

more complete picture of the bank's credit risk profile and with more tools to analyze and control the risk.

In every system, there are major components that feature paramount for the survival of the system. This is also applicable to the financial system. The banking institution had contributed significantly to the effectiveness of the entire financial system as they offer an efficient institutional mechanism through which resources can be mobilized and directed from less essential uses to more productive investments (Wilner,2000).

In the performance of this financial inter-mediation role, the financial institutions have proved to be an effective channel between savers and borrowers. Among the financial institutions that make themselves available for this all-important role are commercial banks, merchant banks, savings banks, the Central bank and development banks. Commercial banks have overtime become very important institutions in the financial system as they function as retail banking units facilitating the transfer of financial assets that are well desired from some part of the public (Fund Lenders) into other financial assets which are more widely preferred by greater part of the public (fund seekers). In view of this role and of the fact that the activities of the commercial banks affect the greater part of the society, commercial banks are selected as the main focus of this study.

Bank's liquidity indicates the ability of commercial banks to finance its transactions efficiently. If the bank is unable to do this it is known as the liquidity risk. As this risk increases the bank is considered unable to meet its obligations (such as deposits withdrawal, debt maturity and investment). Bank for International Settlements (BIS, 2008) explains liquidity as bank's ability to finance increases in assets and meets its obligations without losses. A bank should acquire proper liquidities when needed immediately at a sensible cost.

Banking liquidity represents the capacity of a bank to finance itself efficiently in the course of its transactions or operations. The liquidity risk, for a bank, is the expression of the probability of losing the capacity of financing its transactions, respectively of the probability that the bank cannot honor its obligations to its clients (withdrawal of deposits, maturity of other debt, and cover additional funding requirements for the loan portfolio and investment) The management of the liquidity risk presents important at least from two points of view: primarily an inadequate level of liquidity may lead to the need to attract additional sources of with higher costs reducing profitability of the bank that will lead ultimately insolvency; and secondly an excessive liquidity may lead to a decrease of the return on assets and in consequence poor financial performance.

A bank has a potential of appropriate liquidities when it's in condition to obtain the funds immediately and at a reasonable cost, when these are necessary. In practice, achieving and maintaining optimum liquidity is a real art of bank management. Maintaining an adequate degree of liquidity in the whole banking system is extremely important, because the registration of a liquidity crisis at a single bank can have negative repercussions over the whole banking system thanks to the risk of contagion through interbank settlements.

The main issue here involves establishing the relationship between Loan Portfolio Management and liquidity of observed banks.

1.2 **Statement of the Problem**

Credit creation is the main income generating activity of banks (Kargi, 2011 cited in Kolapo et al, 2012) Loan Portfolio management (LPM) by Commercial Banks is a critical and integral function of lending banks. Due to the nature of some loan being unsecured, poor collateral securities pledged under provision and lack provision for bad and doubtful debts, these banks

encounter a lot of predicaments classify most of the loans and advances as bad and doubtful debts in their balance sheets.

Liquidity management of a commercial bank on the other hand, is a very vital issue in the banking industry. It is the ability of the bank to manage its liquidity position so that neither the liquidity nor the profitable will suffer. In a bid to evaluate if LPM has any indication in the overall effectiveness of the liquidity of commercial banks is an eye opener for this study.

In order to solve the problem of non-performing loans, Commercial Banks have put in place its conservative lending policy which has been integrated with the Commercial Bank prudential guidelines which are jointly aimed at achieving the objectives of the banks. The major problem is, that of devising an appropriate lending principles, set effective standard for evaluating credit worthiness of customer, employ efficient procedure for processing loan and advances and to implement monetary control and recovery of loan and advances in order to alleviate the problem of bad and doubtful loans or reduce it to the barest minimum.

The success of Commercial Banks largely depend on the effectiveness of their credit and loan management system, because these institution generate most of their income from interest earned on loan extended to small and medium entrepreneurs and individual customers. The Central Bank Annual Supervisions Report (2010) indicated high incidence of credit risk reflected in the rising level of non-performing loans by Commercial Banks in the last two (2) decades, a situation that has adversely affected on their liquidity. This trend not only threatens the viability and sustainability of the Commercial Banks but also hinders the achievement of the goals for which they were intended. Loan recovery system is a topic of considerable interest by many researchers. However, most studies undertaken in the past few years focuses mainly on credit models used by Commercial Banks and their impact on profitability (Mgin, 2002). Absence of

empirical studies on Loan Portfolio Management and recognition of the critical role it plays on Commercial Banks liquidity are the principle motivation behind this study which sought to find out the effect of loan Portfolio management on Liquidity in Commercial Banks.

1.3 **Research Questions**

Efforts aimed at holistically analysing the issues raised above have aroused striking inquiries which have brought about questions of the research outlined below;

1. What effect does Asset quality ratio has on current assets of commercial banks?
2. What relationship exists between loan to deposit ratio and liquidity ratio of selected banks in Nigeria?
3. What is the association among asset quality, loan to deposit ratio and liquidity ratio, current ratio?

1.4 **Objectives of the study**

The broad objective of this study is to critically examine the effect of Loan portfolio management on Liquidity.

Specifically, the study intends to achieve the following objectives which are to:

- i. Analyse the effect of asset quality ratio on current assets of commercials banks.
- ii. Analyse the relationship between loan to deposit ratio and the liquidity ratio of selected banks in Nigeria.
- iii. Evaluate the association of asset quality ratio, loan to deposit ratio and liquidity ratio, current assets.

1.5 **Statement of Research Hypothesis**

The following hypotheses are developed to break down and to answer the above mentioned research questions. Therefore, this research work attempts to test the following hypotheses in the case of commercial banks in Nigeria.

H1: The asset quality ratio does have any effect current assets of commercial banks

H2: There is no relationship between loan to deposit ratio and the liquidity ratio of selected banks in Nigeria.

H3: There is no association among asset quality ratio, loan to deposit ratio and liquidity ratio, current ratio.

1.6 **Justification of the Study**

The importance of Loan portfolio management (LPM) on banks liquidity cannot be over – emphasized. Since not more contribution was made in the topic LPM, the researcher will carefully examine those relevant areas considering LPM and its effect on liquidity for a successful banking operation. Where careful consideration will be given to the lending policies of the observed banks as well as issues affecting loans such as default in fulfilling obligations by the debtor.

Hitherto, researchers have focused on loan in respect of profitability or rather performance of commercial banks not much have been said of how loan portfolio of banks affect the liquidity in these commercial banks. Also, studies that managed to cover this key topic observed the period before the banking reform consolidation policy of the central bank of Nigeria in 2005. For this study the period covered is a major distinction and relevance for the topic as it shows the current situation of commercial banks in respect to LPM and liquidity.

It is hoped that the result obtained from the study will be of benefit to banks and the non-bank financial institution, business enterprise and student of banking and finance and other related course.

Readers of this study/work are exposed as regarding the input of future study or further research on this area of study in the banking sector. The basis of this research work is the position of LPM on the Nigerian commercial bank liquidity.

1.7 Scope of the study

This research study considers three (3) Nigerian commercial banks First Bank of Nigeria Plc, Zenith Bank plc, and Guaranty trust bank plc. Simultaneously, collecting data through secondary medium for a space of 10 years from 2005 – 2014. The study will focus on the Nigerian community and how it relates to the topic.

1.8 Limitation of the Study

In study of this nature which involve the analysis of the commercial bank statement and qualification of their investment and degree of their liquidity. In such a study, the limitability of the data available and its type obviously limits the extent and scope of the analysis. The research examined how the commercial banks carry out effectively their portfolio management with respect to their liquidity in the following areas;

- a. Loan and advance
- b. Investment in security E.g. treasury bill.
- c. Balance held with and for other bank.

Internally and still meets their depositors and shareholders demand.

The lending pattern of the Nigerian commercial bank to various sector of the economy will be critically examined. The nature of their loan maturity and an appraised or the step commercial bank takes to cover their debt when customers default their loan repayment agreement.

In this regard, the management of commercial bank loan portfolio management will be discussed. The review of liquidity management theories will be carried out. The management of the asset and liability which means the source of fund are acquired and the use in which they are put are found in the statement of financial position of the bank.

Liquidity position will be looked into and the extent to which commercial banks adhere to the liquidity ratio as set by the central bank of Nigeria.

The research will be limited to commercial bank liquidity and loan issues and management.

The study will be carried out purely as an academic excise and therefore will not receive any form government or will be financed be any private business organization. The limited resources of the researcher may constrain the study.

1.9 Structure of the Study

The research is intended to analyse the problems associated with the management of loan in Nigeria commercial Bank, as it relates to liquidity of Commercial Banks.

Chapter one presented the general introduction of Management of Loan Portfolio in Commercial Banks with particular reference to First Bank of Nigeria Plc, Zenith bank plc and Guaranty Trust bank plc.

Chapter two begins by stressing the most important and distinguished function of Commercial Banks which is creation of credit or money through lending and investing putting in mind their profit maximization objective. The chapter reviews lending principles and loan analysis in

Commercial Banks looking at the safety principles, the profitability principles and suitability principles.

In the chapter three the methodology of the study is presented. This discussion focuses on issues such as the sample size and selection, data collection, the research instrument used and the techniques employed for data analysis of the research empirical result.

The findings of the research are presented in the chapter four and are discussed in relation to existing literature. The chapter touched on the presentation and analysis of data collected from the field and in-depth analysis of the data.

Chapter five present the summary, conclusion and the recommendations of the study in terms of loan portfolio management effect on liquidity of commercial banks.

Bibliography (references) assembled all relevant and accredited authors' literature duly used in this study and lastly, appendices featured at the end of the entire document.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

One of the most important functions of commercial banks is the creation of credit or money. This function distinguishes commercial banks from other financial institutions. The creation of credit is accomplished by the lending and investing activities of commercial banks in corporation with the Central Bank of the Nation.

Since there are many studies in respect of bank's lending behaviour, it is therefore imperative to highlight and consider some factor that economist and professionals alike have proposed as virtually significant in explaining the determinants of commercial banks lending behaviour.

2.2 CONCEPTUAL REVIEWS

Loan portfolio constitutes loans that have been made or bought and are being held for repayment. Loan portfolios are the major asset of commercial banks and the lending institution. The value of the loan portfolio depends not only on the interest rates earned on loans but also on the likelihood that interest and principal will be paid (Jasson, 2002). Lending is the principal business activity for most commercial banks, the loan portfolio is typically the largest asset and the predominate source of revenue. As such, it is one of the greatest sources of risk to a financial institution's safety and soundness. Whether due to lax credit standards, poor portfolio risk management, or weakness in the economy, loan portfolio problems have historically been the major cause of losses and failures. Effective management of the loan portfolio and the credit function is fundamental to a Sacco's safety and soundness. Loan portfolio management (LPM) is

the process by which risks that are inherent in the credit process are managed and controlled. Because review of the LPM process is so important, it is a primary supervisory activity (Koch2000).

The main objective of a commercial bank is profit maximization and to achieve its set up goals and objectives, the banks accept cash as deposits and lend out some of it on credit to borrowers. When a bank advances a loan, it opens an account in the name of the borrower and does not pay him in cash but allows him to draw the money by cheque according to his needs.

When a bank grants a loan, it has actively created a claim against itself and in favour of a borrower.

As earlier stated in the introductory chapter, bad and doubtful debts are the cumulative outcome of errors committed by lending officers in the management of loanable funds available to commercial banks. A clear perspective of the causes and control of bad debts in commercial banks is manifested through in-depth review of literature discussion of common lending that is steps expected to be followed by lending officers while considering loan application of customers. Such lending steps are regarded as fundamental to the growth of good accounts and reductions or otherwise of bad accounts in the commercial banks thereby leading to liquidity problems. In addition, an attempt is hereby made to review the findings and reviews of some researches in the same field regarding the effect loan portfolio of banks have on liquidity in commercial banks.

Banking industries brings into being the most important conduct of money supply and demand deposits through the creation of credits in form of loans and investments. Most of the financial experts agree that loans officers should consider while embarking on lending, the three fundamental C's of credit, which is character of the borrowers, the capital, and the competence

of the borrower or the borrowing company before such loan is granted. The task of the competent bank management is to perform the economic function inherent in the banking industries in such a way as to minimize the return invested fund overtime without taking excessive risk of making huge losses. It is certain that no matter how efficient and effective a bank is, it must still face the question of how to avoid risks that normally result from normal banking operations.

2.2.1 Types of Loans

Commercial banks prefer to grant loans to customers with a very short repayments period usually one year or less. They are the main source of short-term loans that are likely to be generated for immediate financial needs. Short term loan simply refer to loan that has a time of one year or less. However, such loan fails to meet all the needs of the customers and because of this and other interactive outlets for banks fund, it appears banks quite generally have forsaken the ideal loan practice of the theorist and embarked upon a widely varied loan programme.

To this end, commercial bank loan is classified into various forms based on the purpose of the loan. These classes includes among others:

- i. Loans to Business (commercial and industrial enterprise)
- ii. Loans to Agriculture for current purposes
- iii. Loans for Purchasing and carrying securities
- iv. Loans on real estate mortgages and
- v. Loans to Customers.

All these loans are either secured or unsecured

2.2.2 Lending policies

Nnanna, (2005), stressed that “Bank lending decisions generally are fraught with a great deal of risks, which calls for a great deal of caution and tact in this aspect of banking operations. The success of every lending activity to a great extent therefore, hinges on the part of the credit analysts to carry out good credit analysis, presentation, structuring and reporting.

The elements of a loan policy are determined by the specific lending activities and standards of each bank. However, most loan policies follow the outlined procedure

Loan Authority

The lending policy should describe who is authorized to approve credit and should establish specific approval limits for credit approvers. Lending limits may also be set for a group, allowing a combination of officers or a committee to approve loans larger than the members would be permitted to approve individually. Group approval may include dual controls: one approver from the line business unit and another from credit policy or a different line unit. The policy should describe reporting procedures and the frequency of committee meetings. Loan approval systems need to have sufficient flexibility to respond to unanticipated needs while maintaining adequate controls to prevent unwarranted risk.

Limit on Aggregate Loans and Commitments

The loan policy may establish guidelines on the size of the loan portfolio relative to other balance sheet accounts (some banks will cover this topic in the ALCO policy). Limits should be developed for the aggregate volume of outstanding loans as well as for total commitments. A

bank will find it much easier to develop a commitment limit if it has historical data on usage of its commitments during various phases of the credit cycle.

Distribution by Loan Category and Product: Policies also establish guidelines on the percentage of total loans that can be allocated to a particular loan category or concentration (e.g., commercial, real estate, consumer, international, and health care). Limits may also be placed on individual loan products within a loan category. For example, although a bank may already limit consumer loans in general, it can also limit installment loans or credit card loans. Loan category and product limits enable a bank to direct the composition of its loan portfolio to achieve strategic objectives rather than deferring to the demands of its market.

Geographic Limits: The bank's geographic market should be identified, including any exceptions or specific restrictions. Geographic limits are consistent with the objective of serving the credit needs of the bank's community. They also help to ensure that the lending staff can supervise the loan portfolio effectively. Such supervision is especially important for new banks. Furthermore, various risks were identified in the controllers handbook (1999), that hinges on lending activities of commercial banks such risks which include credit, interest rate, liquidity, price, foreign exchange, transaction, compliance, strategic, and reputation. Banks with international operations are also subject to country risk and transfer risk. Highlighting a few which are directly effecting lending

2.2.3 Liquidity risk

Because of the size of the loan portfolio, effective management of liquidity risk requires that there be close ties to, and good information flow from, the lending function. Obviously, loans are a primary use of funds. And while controlling loan growth has always been a large part of liquidity management, historically the loan portfolio has not been viewed as a significant source of funds for liquidity management. Practices are changing, however. Banks can use the loan portfolio as a source of funds by reducing the total dollar volume of loans through sales, securitization, and portfolio run-off.

Recently, banks are taking a more active role in managing their loan portfolios. While these activities are often initiated to manage credit risk, they have also improved liquidity. Banks increasingly are originating loans “for sale” or securitization. Consumer loans are routinely originated for immediate securitization. Many larger banks have been expanding their underwriting for the syndicated loan market. Additionally, banks are also expanding the packaging and sale of distressed credits and otherwise undesirable loans.

2.2.4 Credit Risk

The risk of repayment, i.e., the possibility that an obligor will fail to perform as agreed, is either lessened or increased by a bank’s credit risk management practices. A bank’s first defense against excessive credit risk is the initial credit granting process sound underwriting standards, an efficient, balanced approval process, and a competent lending staff. Because a bank cannot easily overcome borrowers with questionable capacity or character, these factors exert a strong influence on credit quality.

Traditionally, banks have focused on oversight of individual loans in managing their overall credit risk. While this focus is important, banks should also view credit risk management in terms of portfolio segments and the entire portfolio. The focus on managing individual credit risk did not avert the credit crises of the 1980s. However, had the portfolio approach to risk management augmented these traditional risk management practices, banks might have at least reduced their losses.

2.3 BANK LIQUIDITY

Diamond and Dybvig (1983) emphasize the “preference for liquidity” under uncertainty of economic agents to justify the existence of banks: banks exist because they provide better liquidity insurance than financial markets. However, as banks are liquidity insurers, they face transformation risk and are exposed to the risk of run on deposits. More generally, the higher is liquidity creation to the external public, the higher is the risk for banks to face losses from having to dispose of illiquid assets to meet the liquidity demands of customers.

A natural justification for the existence of deposit-taking institutions, thereby giving also an explanation for the economically important role of banks in providing liquidity, was initially modeled by (Bryant 1980 and Diamond and Dybvig 1983). They showed that by investing in illiquid loans and financing them with demandable deposits, banks can be described as pools of liquidity in order to provide households with insurance against idiosyncratic consumption shocks. However, this structure is also the source of a potential fragility of banks since in case of an unexpected high number of depositors deciding to withdraw their funds for other reasons than

liquidity needs, a bank run will result. Both papers stand in the tradition of prior research on the liquidity of assets, for example by (Tobin 1965 or Niehans 1978) as well as on bank runs, by (Friedman and Schwartz 1963).

2.4 THEORETICAL REVIEWS

In the process of continuous evaluation for banks' financial performance, the academicians, researchers, scholars and administrators have made several studies on the Bankometer's models but in different perspectives and in different periods. And they are as follows:

The study of Anita & Shveta (2012) attempted to evaluate the solvency of 37 Indian Commercial banks using Bankometer's model, covering the period of 07/2006 to 11/2010. The findings of this study revealed that private sector banks has performed well and are financially more sound as compared to public sector banks. Top five financially sound banks include Kotak Mahindra, Federal, ICICI, HDFC and Development Credit Bank. The Worst five banks include Central Bank of India, UCO, Syndicate Bank, Bank of Maharashtra and State Bank of Travancore.

Bhattacharya (1997) found that during the post liberalization ear efficiency of public sector banks declined whereas that of private and foreign banks has improved overtime. Maria, Silva and Thannassoulis (2003) evaluated the Japanese banks and concluded that major problem of failed banks was not the inefficiency of management but the below standard capital adequacy ratio and considerable problem in their asset quality. According to Kumbhakar and Sarkar (2003) revealed that the performance of private sector banks but not the public sector banks have improved in response to deregulation measures. Das and Ghosh (2006) found a close relationship between the efficiency and soundness of banks as determined by capital adequacy ratio. The study of Kumar and Gulati (2008) exhibited that the overall technical inefficiency of Indian

commercial banks was due to both poor input utilization and failure to operate at most productive scale size. Wu and Zhang (2005) found that industry factors and the corporate size played a great role in affecting the financial distress: cost of financial distress became great when enterprise in financial distress stood in a poor business environment, and asset size of enterprises had a positive relationship with financial distress cost. According to the Nimalathasan (2008), it is evident from the discussion that average financial position of selected listed manufacturing companies was not sound during the period under study. Moreover, test of the soundness as revealed by Z score (Altman Model) showed that the selected companies were on verge of failure.

Derviz et al. (2008) investigated the determinants of the movements in the long term Standard & Poor's and CAMEL bank ratings in the Czech Republic during the period when the three biggest banks, representing approximately 60% of the Czech banking sector's total assets, were privatized (i.e., the time span 1998-2001).

Gupta and Kaur (2008) conducted the study with the main objective to assess the performance of Indian Private Sector Banks on the basis of Camel Model and gave rating to top five and bottom five banks. They ranked 20 old and 10 new private sector banks on the basis of CAMEL model. They considered the financial data for the period of five years i.e., from 7/2003.

Osayameh (1996) states that, the major objective of commercial banks' lending is to maximize profit. The staggering increase in volume of banks credit in Nigeria in 2005 alone lends credence to this assertion. In 2005, aggregate banks credit to the internal economy grew by 30.8% to a staggering increase of N2,007.4 billion compared with the rate of 22.5 per cent, while credit to the core private sector increased by 29.4 per cent to N1,950 billion(CBN).

Management of such resources should therefore transcend the use of traditional techniques based mainly on the use of rule-of thumb, hunches and experience. The present volume and complexity of transaction in bank lending and credit administration in Nigeria call for the use of scientific techniques like those of management science and operations research to aid their lending and credit administration. Ojo (1999), in a study on roles and failure of financial intermediation by banks in Nigeria revealed that, “commercial banks can lend on medium and short term basis without necessarily jeopardizing their liquidity.

Carletti et al (2006) however, discussing on multiple-lending is of the opinion that banks choose to share lending whenever the benefit of greater diversification, in terms of higher cost per project monitoring dominates the cost of free-riding and duplication of efforts.

If banks set interest rates too high, they may induce adverse selection problems because high-risk borrowers are willing to accept these high rates. Once these borrowers receive the loans, they may develop moral hazard behavior or so called borrower moral hazard since they are likely to take on highly risky projects or investments (Chodecai, 2004).

2.4.1 Portfolio Theory

Banks have been competing harder over market shares and profits. These firms have of late been facing a very unique challenge; how to extract high levels of profit while still maintaining their foundations as lending institutions. Lending is not a very profitable business, the risk of default coupled with the competition driving down market prices have made lending a less attractive enterprise particularly considering liquidity. Therefore some banks are trying to concentrate on their more profitable activities (i.e. advisories, debt and equity sales, mergers and acquisitions). But to be able to extract this sort of business requires banks to engage in loans. Without loans

customers have no incentive to do business with them, since one of their primary needs is to finance their commercial activities through debt. Portfolio theory gives these lending institutions a tool to minimize the risks and hazards of lending therefore stabilizing liquidity.

Portfolio theory was first published by Fischer Black and Myron Scholes in 1973. This model provided banks with a strategy on how to diversify their loans and investments. Before this, banks had no real investment strategy and their only option was to obtain as much collateral as possible and make default an unattractive option. Portfolio Theory allows companies or investors to diversify their investment so to minimize risk and maximize gain. The principle behind the Black – Scholes model is to diversify your equity so that your lowest risk bond produces the same risk as your highest risk investment. When your investments have reached this equilibrium, then risk minimization has been achieved.

Portfolio theory is an integral part of today's financial industry and has provided banks with a very important tool in combating defaults, profit losses as well as maintaining reasonable liquidity. Unfortunately, even these tools aren't perfect and the elimination of risk is an impossibility in this ever changing world. But given future refinement of this model along with further computerization, experience and new tools, default risk may become even further mitigated.

2.4.2 CREDIT RISK THEORY

(Ken Brown & Peter Moles, 2012). Managing credit risk is a complex multidimensional problem and as a result there are a number of different approaches in use, some of which are quantitative while others involve qualitative judgements. Whatever the method used, the key element is to

understand the behavior and predict the likelihood of particular credits defaulting on their obligations.

When the amount that can be lost from a default by a particular set of firms is the same, a higher likelihood of loss is indicative of greater credit risk. In cases where the amount that can be lost is different, we need to factor in not just the probability of default but also the expected loss given default.

2.4.3 Assessing Credit Risk

Assessing credit risk requires us to model the probability of a counter party defaulting in full, or in part, on its obligation. We can picture the credit decision in terms of the basic risk management model. This involves a decision either (A) to extend credit, which provides a reward but entails a risk, or (B) to refuse credit. The situation facing the credit manager is shown as a decision problem in Figure 1.1. The requirement is to balance the gain from taking the credit risk by extending credit against the potential loss. In the decision problem the alternative is to refuse credit and not obtain any reward.

Fig 1

The credit decision as a decision problem

In this model, boxes designate decisions and circles designate outcomes

2.5 EMPIRICAL REVIEWS

Allen (1997) addresses a little examined intersection between the problem loan literature and the bank efficiency literature. Granger-causality techniques are employed to test four hypotheses regarding the relationships among loan quality, cost efficiency, and bank capital. The data suggest that problem loans precede reductions in measured cost efficiency; that measured cost efficiency precedes reductions in problem loans; and that reductions in capital at thinly capitalized banks precede increases in problem loans. Hence, cost efficiency may be an important indicator of future loans and problem banks. Our results are ambiguous concerning whether or not researchers should control for problem loans in efficiency estimation.

Guarav (2010) in a paper titled Principles of Good Lending Every Banker follows loans. Method employed was the Johanson and Juselius cointegration to test if adhering to principles of good lending could guarantee effective loan portfolio management. Findings were positive, describing an ideal advances as “one which is granted to a reliable customer for an approved purpose in which the customer has adequate experience, safe in the knowledge that the money will be used to advantage and repayment will be made within a reasonable period from trading receipts or known maturities due on or about given dates”.

Loan Portfolio Management by Comptroller’s Handbook (2010) emphasizes report. The lending policy may describe the types, contents, and frequency of reports provided to senior management and the board of directors. Common management reports include summaries of the level and trends of loans that are delinquent, nonaccrual, nonperforming, or charged off. It should also include reports on portfolio composition such as concentrations and policy exceptions. Reports on larger problem credits should include information on the level of risk, loss potential, and

alternative courses of action. In the view of Nwankwo (2000), “credit constitutes the largest single income-earning asset in the portfolio of most banks. This explains why banks spend enormous resources to estimate, monitor and manage credit quality”.

Asarnow (1996) in his article “Best Practices in Loan Portfolio Management” describes benchmark to a portfolio management approach. An equally weighted composite benchmark was constructed using the performance results of these loans as reported by Lipper Analytics. The key performance measure observed as total return. Total return is defined as coupon return (payments from the borrower to the investor under the loan contract) plus price return (changes in the market value of the loan, including defaults). In the case of the loan funds, price return is defined as changes in the net asset value of fund units

Valla and Saer Escorbia (2006) studied the liquidity measures for banks in England. They found that profitability, Growth in the credit, GDP, monetary policy, interest rates have a negative impact on bank liquidity. However, in the view of Nwankwo (2000), “credit constitutes the largest single income-earning asset in the portfolio of most banks. This explains why banks spend enormous resources to estimate, monitor and manage credit quality”.

2.6 METHODOLOGY REVIEW

In accessing methods adopted by renowned scholars and authors alike, a spectrum of this is needed in order to establish prominent method which was prevalent among them.

(Parvesh and Afroze, 2014). while discussing capital adequacy determinants in India bank found adopted the multiple regression model for their study of the banks. In their study determinants of capital adequacy includes loan portfolio and management effectiveness. While Julius (2013) in his work impact of loan portfolio management in commercial banks used the ordinary least

squares (OLS) model Kargi (2011) in his study “Credit Risk and the Performance of Nigerian Banks” which measured profitability with Return on Asset (ROA) as a function of the ratio of Non-performing loan to loan & Advances (NPL/LA) and ratio of Total loan & Advances to Total deposit (LA/TD) used as indicators of credit risk.

Tseganesh (2012), in explaining the determinants of liquidity of commercial banks in Ethiopia conducted series of tests which includes ratio analysis of return of assets (ROA), Capital adequacy ratio (CAR) and non-performing loan to total loans (NPL) while also running a regression model to see how the changes in the explanatory variables (x) effect the ‘explained variable (y)

Conclusively, it can be observed from the review that studies carried out on loan portfolio or credit management of banks in terms of liquidity have employed various methods as well as conflicting results or conclusion. While some scholars assert that cognizance of the loan portfolio of banks is important to the liquidity position of such banks, some others suggest there is no correlation between loan portfolio and liquidity implying that how banks handle their loan portfolio does not significantly impact banks liquidity.

However, this study taking the spectrum of information available as well as those not considered in previous related studies, evaluates what relationship exist between LPM of commercial banks and liquidity.

The method adopted prominent in previous research is the regression analysis while few studies employed other methods like CAMEL and others.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter describes and analyses the specific methods employed in showing the relationship between loan portfolio management and liquidity. This chapter describes the techniques and procedures used by the researcher in conducting the study and accumulating data for the study. It comprises of the description of research design, population, data collection methods, Research procedures, Model specification, description of variables and Estimation techniques.

3.2 RESEARCH DESIGN

The study seeks to describe the relationship that exists between loan portfolio, liquidity and other factors on Loan portfolio. The method of this study is quantitative. It uses panel least square regression model to analyze data collected from the annual reports of the selected commercial banks.

3.3 POPULATION

The population of this study is made of all commercial banks in Nigeria.

3.4 SAMPLE SIZE

For the purpose of this study, the researcher adopts the purposive or judgemental sampling method to select the sampled banks for this study based on the following criteria;

1. Banks with high variation in their loan and advances within the period under review.
2. Banks that produce high profitability ratios over the period under study
3. The banks that were operational and have complete financial statements for the period under review.

Therefore, First Bank Nig. Plc., Zenith Bank Plc and Guaranty Trust Bank out of the 21 Commercial Banks operating in Nigeria as at December 2015 as the sample for this research.

3.5 SOURCES OF DATA

This study mainly employs secondary sources of data. The secondary data were extracted from the annual reports of the sampled banks for the period under review (i.e. 2005 – 2014). Also relevant literature on the effect of loan portfolio management policies on liquidity of banks were obtained, precisely from related journals, articles, textbooks relevant to this study and the annual financial reports of selected banks.

Definition of Variables

- **Dependent Variable**

This is the variable that is being predicted in this study. The dependent variables in this study is the Liquidity which is proxied by Current Ratio and Current asset

CURRENT RATIO: It is a measure of a firm or banks ability to meet its short-term obligations. The current ratio is calculated by dividing current assets by current liabilities.it is also called liquidity ratio.

$$CR = \frac{\text{Current Asset}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

- **Independent Variable**

The independent variable is the variable that is used as a base for prediction. Under this study the independent variable are Asset Quality Ratios and loan to deposit ratio

Asset Quality Ratios

An asset quality rating is a review or evaluation assessing the credit risk associated with a particular asset. These assets usually require interest payments - such as a loans and investment portfolios. How effective management is in controlling and monitoring credit risk can also have an effect on the what kind of credit rating is given.

$$\text{AQR} = \frac{\text{Loan loss reserves}}{\text{Average loans}}$$

Loan-To-Deposit Ratio

The loan-to-deposit ratio (LTD) is a commonly used statistic for assessing a bank's liquidity by dividing the banks total loans by its total deposits. This number, also known as the LTD ratio, is expressed as a percentage. If the ratio is too high, it means that banks might not have enough liquidity to cover any unforeseen fund requirements; if the ratio is too low, banks may not be earning as much as they could be.

$$\text{LTD} = \frac{\text{Average net loans}}{\text{Average deposit}}$$

Loan Portfolio Profitability (LLP)

This is expressed as interest income attributable to advances minus provision for bad and doubtful loans divided by gross loans and advances. Thus, loan portfolio profitability = (interest income attributable to advances - provision for bad and doubtful loans) / gross loans and advances

3.6 MODEL SPECIFICATION

The model for this study is made in line with the objectives of the study. The study tends to find the effect of asset quality ratio and loan to deposit ratio on current asset stability of commercial banks. To make the model more robust loan portfolio probability is added to the model. Therefore the model is specified as;

Current Ratio= F (Asset quality ratio, loan to deposit ratio, loan portfolio probability μ)

CR= F (AQR, LTD, LPP, μ)

Explicitly, the model to determine the effect of loan portfolio management on liquidity is in Nigeria is written as follows:

$$CR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AQR + \beta_2 LTD + \beta_3 LPP + \mu$$

Where;

CR= Current ratio

AQR= Asset quality ratio

LTD= Loan to deposit ratio

LPP= Loan portfolio probability

β_0 = intercept

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \& \beta_3$ =coefficient

μ = stochastic error term

3.7 DESCRIPTION OF VARIABLES

The variables for this study are available as secondary financial data and they will be captured annually. The dependent variable is current ratio (CR). The control variables are; Asset quality ratio (AQR), Loan to deposit ratio (LTD) and Loan portfolio probability (LPP).

The meanings of the variables in the empirical model have been explained below:

Fig 2

Variables symbol	Measurement unit	Variables explanation
CR	Current ratio	Current asset / current liabilities
AQR	Asset quality ratio	Loan loss reserve / average loans
LTD	Loan to deposit ratio	Average net loan / average deposit
LPP	Loan portfolio profitability	(interest income attributable to advances - provision for bad and doubtful loans) / gross loans and advances.

3.8 DATA ANALYSIS METHOD

Firstly, the correlation of the variables is checked. Secondly, the Panelleast square of the estimation technique of regression analysis is used in the study to examine the causal relationship among the variables. The use of ordinary least square is justified because of its distinguishing attributes. It is said to produce a best linear unbiased estimate.

The estimated parameters are subjected to evaluation by using other test: student t-statistic test and F-statistic test. While, the overall stability of the specified empirical model is tested using multiple co-efficient of determination (R^2), adjusted R^2 and Durbin-Watson test.

The normality of the variables is also checked.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

4.1 INTRODUCTIONS

The goal of this study is to empirically examine the effect of loan portfolio management on liquidity of banks in Nigeria. In order to make the model robust, another explanatory variable was included in order to capture the exact relationship between loan portfolio management and liquidity. This chapter is therefore concerned with the presentation and empirical analysis of results derived from the estimation. In doing this, the ordinary least squares regression technique is utilized in the empirical analysis.

4.2 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Table 1

	CR	AQR	LTD	LPP
Mean	1.140453	0.033683	0.620287	0.18627
Median	1.12495	0.02145	0.6633	0.17515
Maximum	1.4282	0.2864	0.9288	0.3184
Minimum	1.0115	0.0009	0.3562	0.1014
Std. Dev.	0.099439	0.051804	0.163814	0.054664
Skewness	0.990721	4.064426	-0.11069	0.599896
Kurtosis	3.791431	20.26949	1.803923	2.507694
Jarque-Bera	5.690593	455.392	1.849513	2.102331
Probability	0.058117	0	0.396628	0.34953
Sum	34.2136	1.0105	18.6086	5.5881
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.286756	0.077826	0.778217	0.086657
Observations	30	30	30	30

Source: Researcher's computation with the aid of EVIEWS 9

The data for estimating the effect of loan portfolio management on liquidity of banks in Nigeria will be drawn from the 3 selected Banks' Annual Report. The total number of observations is 30.

The mean and the median is used to describe the centre of the data, however for this research the mean will be used as a standard measure of the centre of the distribution because the unusual values and call outliers affect the median more than they affect the mean. The mean value of the current ratio is 1.140; this means that on the average commercial banks have been able to manage their short term obligations well, 1.14:1 is a favorable current ratio as its above the theoretically mandatory 1:1 level. The value of the mean AQR is 0.0336. The mean value of the Loan to deposit ratio is 0.620; this means that on the average commercial banks have loaned out less money than has been deposited by customers. The value of the mean LPP is 0.1862.

The standard deviation shows the spread of the data. The standard deviation of CR is 0.099 which shows that most of the observations are spread within 11 standard deviations on each side of the mean. The standard deviation of AQR is 0.051 which shows that most of the observations are spread very closely to the mean. The standard deviation of LTD is 0.163 which shows that most of the observations are spread within 3 standard deviation on each side of the mean. The standard deviation of LPP is 0.054 which shows that most of the observations are spread within 3 standard deviation to each side of the mean.

An analysis of the Jarque-Bera statistics shows that all the residuals are normally distributed except AQR.

NORMALITY TEST

The Jarque-Bera statistics is used in testing for normality in the residuals. Its value is 0.0718 and its p-value of 0.9647 shows that the null hypothesis of normal distribution cannot be rejected, and thus the residual are normally distributed.

Table 2

Source: Researcher's computation with the aid of EVIEWS 9

4.3 CORRELATIONS

Table 3

Correlation				
t-Statistic				
Probability	CR	AQR	LTD	LPP
CR	1			

AQR	-0.14144	1		
	-0.75603	-----		
	0.4559	-----		
LTD	0.379093	-0.21325	1	
	2.167775	-1.15495	-----	
	0.0388	0.2579	-----	
LPP	0.090252	0.262046	0.76532	1
			-	
	0.479528	1.436829	6.29173	-----
	0.6353	0.1618	0	-----

Source: Researcher's computation with the aid of EVIEWS 9

The correlation results show that the dependent variable CR has weak and negative relationship with AQR, the relationship with AQR is statistically insignificant. CR also has a weakly positive relationship with LTD that is statistically significant. CR has no relationship with LPP. AQR has a weakly correlated and insignificant relationship with LTD and LPP. LTD has an inverse relationship with LPP and the relationship is statistically significant.

The researcher proceeds to use the correlation analysis to test the hypothesis.

Hypothesis 1:

H0= There is no relationship between loan to deposit ratio and the liquidity ratio of selected banks in Nigeria.

H1= There is a relationship between loan to deposit ratio and the liquidity ratio of selected banks in Nigeria.

From the results above we can see that the correlation coefficient of LTD and CR is 0.379093 and its p-value is 0.0388. Therefore, we can say there is a weak positive relationship between the two variables significant at the 1% level.

In conclusion the hypothesis of is no relationship between loan to deposit ratio and the liquidity ratio of selected banks in Nigeria can be rejected. We reject the null hypothesis.

4.4 STATIONARITY TEST

Table 4

variable		P-		P-		CONCLUSION
		PP	VALUE	ADF	VALUE	
CR	Levels	10.8509	0.0931	7.44179	0.2891	I(I,2)
	1st diff	23.8654	0.0006*	7.49823	0.2772	
	2nd diff	27.39	0.0001*	16.1824	0.0128*	
AQR	Levels	21.8949	0.0013*	8.86891	0.1811	I(I)
	1st diff	32.602	0*	6.47677	0.372	
	2nd diff	23.7376	0.0006*	3.34976	0.7638	
LTD	Levels	4.0322	0.6723	7.96011	0.241	I(I,2)
	1st diff	12.571	0.0504	11.2071	0.8222	
	2nd diff	16.5432	0.0111*	18.338	0.0054*	
LPP	Levels	7.54541	0.2733	10.3781	0.1096	I(I)
	1st diff	22.0936	0.0012*	14.3694	0.0258*	
	2nd diff	23.7187	0.0006*	10.1373	0.119	

Source: Researcher's computation with the aid of EVIEWS 9

The results above show that the variable CR is stationary at second difference, the variable AQR is stationary at first difference, the variable LTD is stationary at second difference and the variable LPP is stationary at first difference.

4.5 COINTEGRATION

Table 5

	Statistic	Prob.	WEIGHTED	
			Statistic	Prob.
Panel v-Statistic	-0.99982	0.8413	-1.054622	0.8542
Panel rho-Statistic	1.017667	0.8456	1.273964	0.8987
Panel PP-Statistic	-0.295	0.384	0.538255	0.7048
Panel ADF-Statistic	-0.32935	0.3709	0.497221	0.6905

Source: Researcher's computation with the aid of EVIEWS 9

The panel co-integration results show that the variables are not co-integrated, i.e there is no long run associationship between the variables.

4.6 PANEL VAR MODEL

Dependent variable: CA

Table 6

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	6.78E+08	8.20E+08	0.826275	0.4216
CA(-1)	1.129972	0.26577	4.251689	0.0007
CA(-2)	-0.008101	0.29128	-0.027812	0.9782
AQR(-1)	-3.40E+09	2.96E+09	-1.149119	0.2685
AQR(-2)	-50214353	1.20E+09	-0.041868	0.9672
LTD(-1)	-7.19E+08	5.40E+08	-1.333194	0.2024
LTD(-2)	1.32E+08	5.59E+08	0.235785	0.8168
LPP(-1)	-5.76E+08	1.88E+09	-0.306312	0.7636
LPP(-2)	-2.53E+08	1.49E+09	-0.169561	0.8676

Source: Researcher's computation with the aid of EVIEWS 9

The VAR is used to explain whether the independent variables have a cause affect on the dependent variable. The wald test was used to check if the independent variables lagged 1 and 2 have cause effect on CA. The results show that all the variables lagged 1 and lagged 2 do not jointly cause CA.

4.7 PANEL LEAST SQUARE RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

DEPENDENT VARIABLE- CR

Table 7

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.42127	2.9483	0.0067
AQR	-0.31208	-1.15161	0.2600
LTD	0.653637	5.086957	0.0000
LPP	1.740768	4.465519	0.0001

$R^2=0.5175$ $ADJ. R^2=0.4618$ $P (F-STATISTIC)=0.00238$ $D.W= 1.54$

Source: Researcher's computation with the aid of EVIEWS 9

The panel least squares result in the table shows that all the independent variables is significant except AQR. It is seen that Asset quality ratio (AQR) has a negative relationship with Current ratio (CR) which is in line with the a-priori expectation, it also has a probability that is insignificant. Loan to deposit ratio (LTD) has a positive relationship with current ratio (CR) and a probability which is significant at the 1% conservative level, its coefficient is 0.6536 which indicates that a unit increase in the value of Loan to deposit ratio leads to about 0.6536 unit increase in current asset ratio. Loan portfolio probability (LPP) has a positive relationship with dependent variable CR, the relationship is statistically significant.

4.7 COEFFICIENT OF DETERMINATION AND F-STATISTICS

In measuring the explanatory power of the model, the adjusted R-squared showed that the model explained just 46.18% systematic variation in current assets this leaves only 56.82% unexplained variation which is captured by other factors that affect current assets that are not captured in the model. The F-statistics which measures the robustness of the variables put together indicates statistical significance at the 1% level and thus shows that the explanatory variables are significant altogether.

OLS RESULTS (Table 8)

Dependent Variable: CR
Method: Panel Least Squares
Date: 11/19/16 Time: 15:12
Sample: 2005 2014
Periods included: 10
Cross-sections included: 3
Total panel (balanced) observations: 30

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CR	0.421270	0.142886	2.948300	0.0067
AQR	-0.312084	0.270998	-1.151611	0.2600
LTD	0.653637	0.128493	5.086957	0.0000
LPP	1.740768	0.389824	4.465519	0.0001
R-squared	0.517565	Mean dependent var	1.140453	
Adjusted R-squared	0.461899	S.D. dependent var	0.099439	
S.E. of regression	0.072944	Akaike info criterion	-2.274686	
Sum squared resid	0.138341	Schwarz criterion	-2.087859	
Log likelihood	38.12028	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-2.214918	
F-statistic	9.297756	Durbin-Watson stat	1.546713	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000238			

Source: Researcher's computation with the aid of EVIEWS

4.8.2 TESTING FOR AUTOCORRELATION

The D-W statistics value of 1.54 is close to 2. Therefore we can conclude that there is no autocorrelation problem in the model. The implication of this is that the estimated model is to an extent reliable and good for policy directions.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Introduction

This is the concluding chapter of this research work to examine the effect of loan portfolio management on liquidity of commercial banks. Below is a summary of findings, empirical findings throughout the study, theoretical findings, limitation of the study and suggestion for further findings. This chapter also includes the recommendations and conclusions deduced from the findings in the research work

5.2 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

This study has sought to examine the effect of loan portfolio management on liquidity. This is based on the widely acclaimed view that bank loans have an effect on bank operations. Using data covering the period 2005 to 2014 the panel Least Squares econometric tools was employed to empirically examine the relationship. The empirical results reveal the following findings:

- 1) That asset quality ratio has a negative and insignificant effect on bank liquidity in Nigeria
- 2) That Loan to deposit ratio has a positive and significant effect on bank liquidity in Nigeria.
- 3) Loan portfolio probability has a positive effect on liquidity that is statistically significant.

5.3 CONCLUSION

From the empirical results we can conclude that asset quality ratio has no effect on the current assets of commercial banks. Also we observe there is a positive relationship between loan to deposit ratio and current ratio. Overall we can conclude that the commercial banks have been efficient with giving out loans as it has not affected their liquidity, i.e. they are still able to settle short term obligations as they fall due. The commercial banks have been able to meet demand for both loans and deposits paid to them. The strategic nature of the commercial banks reflects in their liquidity as the current assets are more than the short term obligations.

5.4 RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of our empirical analysis give important policy perspectives for desired action in Nigeria. These include:

- (i) Steps need to be taken to increase bank mobilization.
- (ii) Commercial banks need to be strategic in giving out loans so as to reduce bad debts.
- (iii) Good monetary policies relating to stabilize interest should be adopted as it is critical to bank operations.
- (iv) Commercial banks should analyze loans to be given out carefully so as not to adversely affect bank mobilization.
 - (i) Efforts should be made by Government and policy makers to strive to improve the investment climate and ensure political stability in order to present a robust and healthy economic environment that will make banks want to give out loans that will enhance their operations.

5.5 Limitation of the study

This methodology however has some limitations like other studies on impact of commercial bank on rural transformation.

The researcher was to use the population of the banks quoted on the Nigeria stock Exchange (NSE) to analyze the effect of loan portfolio management on the liquidity of banks in Nigeria. As a result of the unavailability of requisite data (i.e. financial report) of some banks in the NSE fact book and bank website, the sampled population was taken for the study based on availability of requisite data.

One of the pitfalls of the methodology is the use of secondary data. It is consensus opinion that they are not reliable, given that the method used in collecting the data used in the banks report is not known or cannot be verified. Thus, it may or may not have suited the researcher's data collection standard. The data used for this study to a large extent is accurate valid and reliable since it uses data from already audited financial report.

Another limitation is related to the various proxy variables used in the study. The proxy variables issue is a problem common to all empirical testing in bank credit and generally in other areas. Because the proxy remain proxies and may not perfectly represent the theoretical propositions. Although, the proxy variables used in this were defended.

The design of the study is limited as an ex-post facto design, which lack control over the dependent variables. The study is also faced with uncertainty over whether the relevant causal factor(s) is included among the many factors under study. However, significant validity tests, such as VIF, TOL and the generalized R^2 were conducted to ascertain the appropriateness of the models.

Although the regression analysis has its own inherent limitations, the study relies on this method for its objectiveness and scientific approach in data analysis.

Although considerable care has been taken to militate against the expected adverse effect of these identified defects, the results of this study should be interpreted taking into consideration the limitation stated above.

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APPENDIX 1

**DATA GATHERED FROM THE ANNUAL STATEMENT OF SELECTED
COMMERCIAL BANKS**

BANK	YR	CA	CR	AQR	LTD	LPP
GTB	2005	156,399,588	1.2022	0.0177	0.6805	0.2051
GTB	2006	280,727,145	1.0822	0.0211	0.3922	0.2232
GTB	2007	424,604,310	1.1387	0.0063	0.391	0.2541
GTB	2008	861,731,043	1.2636	0.0095	0.9288	0.136
GTB	2009	931588321	1.2362	0.066	0.8126	0.1741
GTB	2010	947887136	1.2241	0.0133	0.7902	0.1428
GTB	2011	1313740723	1.1631	0.0276	0.6649	0.1422
GTB	2012	1380115702	1.2038	0.0009	0.6997	0.1897
GTB	2013	1361379253	1.0248	0.0031	0.7345	0.1603
GTB	2014	1654583370	1.0999	0.0052	0.8213	0.1263
ZENITH	2005	308498697	1.0568	0.0248	0.5248	0.1248
ZENITH	2006	570821103	1.1372	0.0218	0.5083	0.1802
ZENITH	2007	803872754	1.073	0.0277	0.3843	0.2759
ZENITH	2008	1572867566	1.2032	0.0324	0.3562	0.3184
ZENITH	2009	1731471491	1.4282	0.0669	0.6022	0.273
ZENITH	2010	1516379000	1.0728	0.0413	0.5485	0.171
ZENITH	2011	1796366000	1.0115	0.0192	0.5243	0.1762
ZENITH	2012	2076979000	1.047	0.0089	0.4969	0.2288
ZENITH	2013	2567889000	1.0946	0.0088	0.5417	0.231

ZENITH	2014	3226462000	1.224	0.0078	0.6976	0.1644
FIRST	2005	340733	1.0238	0.2864	0.4321	0.2655
FIRST	2006	488740	1.0313	0.0817	0.4494	0.1913
FIRST	2007	700404	1.0557	0.0092	0.3767	0.2302
FIRST	2008	1,529,877	1.352	0.0139	0.6617	0.2111
FIRST	2009	1693514	1.1644	0.0509	0.8219	0.1014
FIRST	2010	1871002	1.1607	0.0489	0.7645	0.1339
FIRST	2011	2118921	1.0727	0.0241	0.7445	0.1212
FIRST	2012	2451799	1.0668	0.0239	0.7513	0.1504
FIRST	2013	3081643	1.1127	0.0225	0.7135	0.1437
FIRST	2014	3189979	1.1866	0.0187	0.7925	0.1419

APPENDIX 2

Dependent Variable: CR

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 11/19/16 Time: 15:12

Sample: 2005 2014

Periods included: 10

Cross-sections included: 3

Total panel (balanced) observations: 30

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CR	0.421270	0.142886	2.948300	0.0067
AQR	-0.312084	0.270998	-1.151611	0.2600
LTD	0.653637	0.128493	5.086957	0.0000
LPP	1.740768	0.389824	4.465519	0.0001
R-squared	0.517565	Mean dependent var	1.140453	
Adjusted R-squared	0.461899	S.D. dependent var	0.099439	
S.E. of regression	0.072944	Akaike info criterion	-2.274686	
Sum squared resid	0.138341	Schwarz criterion	-2.087859	
Log likelihood	38.12028	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-2.214918	
F-statistic	9.297756	Durbin-Watson stat	1.546713	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000238			